

THE CONCEPT OF SMART CITY AND AN INNOVATIVE APPROACH TO URBAN GOVERNANCE OF PUBLIC AFFAIRS

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Abstract

The smart city is a modern idea focused around urban governance carried out with the use of the latest technical and technological achievements (including information technology) that allow to raise the standard of living. The approach is associated with the widely understood economy of resources that fall within the decision-making powers of urban authorities. Consequently, this means the reduction of costs related to the functioning of the city as a whole as well as costs incurred by city users. The paper aims to identify spheres and areas where it is possible to use instruments fully corresponding to the assumptions of the concept of smart governance. Considerations will refer to selected areas of influence of urban authorities in which the use of modern techniques and technologies is a prerequisite for progress in modern times. These areas cover: administration, energy and waste management, urban space, environment, transport and public transportation. The analysis will be strengthened by indicating specific solutions in the framework of the smart concept.

Keywords: city development, *smart city* concept, innovative urban governance

Introduction

Local government plays an important role? in the state and the economic system. Is it a decentralized form? exercise public power and make economic decisions. As a social and political structure, the local government owns large fixed assets, has significant financial resources (budget) and manages large human resources through appropriate organizational units. The listed elements are economic resources, thanks to which it becomes possible to providing good and services to residents local government communities. The activity of a local government in the understanding of the realization of one's own tasks is of a public utility character. Pursuant to the Act on municipal self-government ¹ and the Act on communal management ^{1[326] 2[327]}, all own tasks are of public utility, and their goal is the ongoing and uninterrupted satisfaction of the collective needs of the population by providing services widely available. This means that the municipal (local government) economy includes the tasks of individual local government units.^{3 4}

The aim of the article is an attempt to outline the role and functions of local government at the basic level, ie the city, in undertaking economic activity aimed at local development (growth). Apart from many participants of the urban community, its bodies (authorities), ie the city council, president or mayor, and the administration associated with them, occupy a special place in the decision-making structure. The considerations in the article are theoretical and focus on it is more on outlining the problem than on its in-depth analysis. So far, in the

¹ The Act of March 8, 1990. on the commune self-government, Journal of Laws of 2001, No. 142, item 1591 with poz. D.

² The Act of 20 December 1996. on municipal economy, Journal of Laws of 1997, No. 9, item 43 as amended

References on the subject, the entity running the local politics? development was treated as an aggregate (most often as authorities), while it consists of it consists of three elements (sub-entities), ie the political factor, the executive body and the administration. Of course, the most important subject in the territorial self-government are its inhabitants, who play a role? a kind of sovereign.

1. The role of local government in local entrepreneurship

The city council carries out its own tasks by running a business, irrespective of whether it is profitable or not ^{5[328]}. This activity is carried out on the basis of the possessed economic resources, which are used by launching the management process. The city council is economically active from the economic point of view, as it runs communal entrepreneurship. Thus, local entrepreneurship is understood as activities carried out by local government units for the performance⁶

own tasks, as well as the activity of private and social entities, guided by? with your goals and interests. According to the concept of the so-called new logic of territorial development, city authorities become a significant subject of interference in market mechanisms ^{7[329]} ⁸.

The essence of local government implies the necessity to provide specific public services on a local scale, satisfying the basic, collective needs of residents. These services are of an administrative, technical and social nature

⁵ In the interwar period in Poland, the city council ran two types of business - business: commercial-oriented (slaughterhouses, sawmills, factories) and non-profit-making (public utility enterprises); see A. Ginsbert-Gebert, *Polityka communalna*, PWE, Warsaw 1984, pp. 37-38.

⁷ R. Brol, *Local development - the new logic of economic development*, in: *in theory and practice*, Scientific Papers of the Wroclaw University of Economics No. 785, Wroclaw 1998, pp. 11-15.

^{9[330]} . Administrative services are provided by the office employing clerks. Other municipal services are provided on the basis of facilities classified as technical infrastructure (roads, transport, utilities providing water, energy, drainage) and social infrastructure (educational, health and cultural institutions). Technical services meet the basic needs of people, while social - the so-called the needs of a higher order (according to Maslow's classification) ^{10[331]} ¹¹¹² .

The main goal of the functioning of a local government is local development related to the proper satisfaction of the social needs of members of that local government. This means the necessity to meet all the conditions influencing (stimulating) the course of developmental processes. One of them is the efficient process of providing services (indirect impact). If the city is well organized and equipped with the necessary modern infrastructure, their condition and functioning positively influence possible location decisions. Then the investor does not cover the costs related to the development of the land development. The appearance of the city and its elements and the possibility of organizing free time may encourage or discourage investors from locating their activities in its area.

At the same time, the city authorities pursue a policy, they can, to a certain degree, influence the increase of economic activity, consisting in the increase in the number of economic entities, regardless of their size. There is a common view that only a large, foreign investor is able to heal the situation? economic activity in the city, guide it on the track of rapid economic growth in the city. As

⁹ Cf. K. Pakonski, *Goal-oriented integrated financial management*, Municipium, Warsaw 2001, p. 16.

¹⁰ M. Kostera, *Fundamentals of organization and management*, Wyższa Szkoła Przedsiębiorczości i Zarządzania im. Leon Kozłowski, Warsaw 1998, p. 43.

S. Korenik notes, a more convenient and faster way of influencing the economic development of a commune is the location of a large investment. However, it should be remembered that larger entrepreneurs often transfer profits to other areas in crisis conditions. On the other hand, small entrepreneurs are integrally connected with a given place ^{13[332]}¹⁴. This point of view seems to be however, it is too narrow, as it implies that every new investor is desirable. According to A. Zalewski, "investors do not compete for location, but local and regional authorities compete for attracting investors" ^{15[333]} ¹⁶.

2. The essence of local development

The term "local development" is not uniformly defined, and most often when trying to describe this term, it is features? localities or institutions participating in it. Local development should generally be understood as any positive changes felt by the city's inhabitants (improvement of the quality of life) and entrepreneurs (company development and financial benefits). The essence of local development is progressive changes in three spheres: economic, social and cultural, accompanied by the support of public institutions ^{17[334]}. Local development is a process that involves changes of a quantitative and qualitative-structural nature. According to JJ Paris, local development should be treated very broadly, as economic and social activities, and even equated with

¹³ S. Korenik, *The role of small and medium-sized entrepreneurship in local development (solutions functioning in Poland)*, in: *Local economy in theory and practice*, Scientific Papers of Wrocław University of Economics No. 860, Wrocław 2000, pp. 181-182.

¹⁵ A. Zalewski, *Competition between territorial units and the efficiency of the economy*, in: *Local economy in theory and practice*, Scientific Papers of the University of Economics in Wrocław No. 1124, Wrocław 2006, p. 259.

¹⁷ *Local government and local development*, ed. A. Piekara, Z. Niewiadomski, University of Warsaw, Warsaw 1992, p. 17.

the local economy^{18[335] 19[336]2021 22}. R. Brol believes that local development is the activity of the local community with the participation of other entities in order to improve and create utility values for the area, create conditions for the local economy and ensure spatial and ecological trace. Its result is the creation of new values¹¹.

It draws attention to the importance of the principles of sustainable development in local development? T. Domanski^{23[337]}. It is not an easy process as it requires the reconciliation (harmonization) of three different logics: social, economic and ecological^{24[338]}. A. Zalewski believes that sustainable local development is more a postulate than a reality.²⁵²⁶

Keep in mind the purpose of the article, the most adequate definition? In the economic aspect of local development, EJ Blakely states that local economic development is a process aimed at creating new jobs and revitalizing economic activity^{27[339]}. In turn, A. Klasik also considers new companies and new jobs to

¹⁸ JJ Parysek, *Fundamentals of local economy*, Scientific Publishers of the University of Adama Mickiewicza, Poznan 2001, pp. 46-47

¹⁹ R. Brol, *City development*, in: *Economics and city management*, ed. R. Brol, Wroclaw University of Economics Publishing House, Wroclaw 2004, pp. 201-202.

²³ T. Domanski, *Strategic planning of the economic development of a commune*, Agencja Rozwoju Komunalnej, Warsaw 1999, p. 16.

²⁴ A. Zalewski, *Is Sustainable Local Development Possible ?*, in: *Local economy in theory and practice*, Scientific Works of Wroclaw University of Economics No. 3 (1203), Wroclaw 2008, p. 312.

²⁷ EJ Blakely, *Planning Local Economic Development. Theory and Practice*, SAGE Library of Social Research, 1989, London, after: D. Morisson, *Economic development. Strategic approach to municipal management*, USAID, Agencja Rozwoju Komunalnej, Warsaw 1997, p. 1.

be the content of local economic development^{28[340]2930}. Most authors treat local development as a process of creating new values, including intellectual ones, based on knowledge. Local development in the economic dimension is the basic goal of the policy implemented by the local government in the city. An important conclusion follows from this. Workplaces are primarily created by entrepreneurs and investors, therefore they should be of particular interest to municipal authorities. In a sense, the local government also offers employment in municipal services (units, budgetary enterprises, municipal companies). In small towns, local government offices and organizational units are a significant and attractive place to work on the local market. According to JT Hryniewicz,³¹

3. Instruments of local development policy.

The goals of local development are, as it were, imposed on the local government from outside, constituting a specific "date?" economic. They are obvious because they are with various aspects of local development. The problem is the selection of appropriate (legally defined) tools (methods, techniques, solutions, statutory provisions) oriented towards development goals. In specialist References, different classifications of this type of instruments. According to the popular division, these are the instruments of direct and indirect influence^{32[342]}³³.

²⁸ A. Klasik, *Local development management*, in: *Gmina development management in urban-industrial complexes*, ed. F. Kuznik, PTE, Katowice 1996, p. 16.

³¹ JT Hryniewicz, *Self-government administration - missions, ownership and organizational context*, "Samorzyd Territorial" 2004, No. 10, p. 34.

³² L. Seealek, *Tools for the impact of territorial self-governments on local and regional development*, "Samorzqd Terrialny" 1996, No. 5, pp. 43-45.

For the purposes of this study, the following classification was adopted tools proposed by E. Wojciechowski, who divided the management tools into: development-oriented, organizational, economic and financial, marketing, quality-oriented, infrastructural, transformation, information, efficiency and analytical ^{34[343]35}. Instruments focused on development, organizational, economic and financial as well as infrastructural are of a special nature for entrepreneurs in the city. In turn, planning documentation (and especially spatial development plans) defines the city area with the distribution of its development functions. These functions, along with shaping a positive image, are very important when it comes to attracting potential entrepreneurs. Organizational solutions, the quality of customer service and the information functions of the office are within in the field of municipal administration activities.

As it results from the research conducted under the supervision of P. Swianiewicz, the most significant influence on local economic development are such categories of variables as human capital (education), civic society and infrastructure. Business support institutions, leadership, cooperation and marketing (promotion) are of less importance. The study confirmed the marginal importance of actions focused on reducing the costs of running a business by local enterprises ^{36[344] 37}.

4. Administration as a barrier to entrepreneurship development

Paradoxically, the factors of local development may limit this development - they may be its barrier. An important place in them is the quality of local government administration, which in this case has an internal character, related

³⁴ E. Wojciechowski, *Economy of local government*, Difin, Warsaw 2012, pp. 95-105.

³⁶ P. Swianiewicz, J. Lukomska, *Local government authorities towards local economic development. Which policies are effective ?*, "Samorzqd T Terrialny" 2004, No. 6, pp. 26-27.

to the organizational and institutional system constituting the basic subjects of local development policy. The local government administration manages the city's decision-making body (city council) and works for the executive body (city president). In itself it carries the features of a public authority, as it makes administrative decisions on matters vital to the inhabitants. The city office is a professional official apparatus, it carries out the city's own tasks. Its size grows with the scale of the city ^{38[345]39}. The organization of the office - procedures, style of operation can be both a factor contributing to the client and his service, as well as an element that hinders the settlement of the case by the resident or investor, discouraging them.

Research on the determinants of economic freedom quite clearly indicate the administrative apparatus as a significant factor limiting the development of entrepreneurship. It seems that the barriers? t? can be removed easily enough in a short time. The thing comes down to? to a significant improvement in the quality of administration with a different focus on a potential client, in our case - entrepreneurs.

From international research, the significant importance of public administration as an element of the environment for entrepreneurs conducting business activity. Interesting information is provided by the *Doing Business ranking or the Europe 2020 Competitiveness Report* indexes . In the last ranking, presenting the competitiveness of countries, Poland in 2012 included in 23rd place out of 27 countries of the European Union ^{40[346]} .⁴¹

³⁸ M. Wojciechowski, *The cost of power in the Polish local government*, Difin, Warsaw 2014, pp. 105-107.

⁴⁰ A. Raszowski, *Ranking of EU countries on the example of The Europe 2020 Competitiveness Report*, in: *Regional economy in theory and practice*, ed. D. Strahl, A. Raszowski, D. Gluszczyk, Scientific Papers of the University of Economics in Wroclaw No. 333, Wroclaw 2014, p. 109.

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